

Conductometric Study of the Solvolysis Rates of some Disubstituted Benzyl Bromides

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The rates of solvolysis of benzyl bromide and 2,4-dicyano-benzyl bromide and *p*-carbomethoxybenzyl bromide were obtained conductometrically¹ at 45°, 50° and 55° in 50% aqueous acetone. This technique proved to be superior to other kinetic methods suggested in the literature². The literature methods failed to give reproducible results. The values of rate constants at 45° of the benzyl bromides followed the order: benzyl > *p*-carbomethoxybenzyl > 2,4-dicyano-benzyl bromide. The same order applies to the rate constants of the following benzyl bromides at 50° and 55°: benzyl > *p*-carbomethoxybenzyl > 2,4-dicyanobenzyl bromide.

THE equipment used included a Sargent Constant Temperature Water Bath with a Princo (Magnaset) thermoregulator by Precision Thermometry and Instrument Co. A yellow Scientific Instrument Co., Inc., Model 31 conductivity bridge. A Beckman thermometer generally indicated a maximum range of about $\pm 0.015^\circ\text{C}$.

All melting points were obtained on a Fisher-Johns melting apparatus.

Gas Phase chromatography was carried out on an Aerograph gas chromatograph, using an SE-30 column.

Infrared spectra were obtained on a Beckman I. R. 8 spectrophotometer.

Synthesis: The 2, 4-dicyano and *p*-carbomethoxy benzyl bromides were synthesised by the methods of Newman and Boden³ with pyridine and modified with *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone by Friedman and Shechter.^{4,5}

Kinetic procedure: The rates of solvolysis of the benzyl bromides were obtained by taking 50 ml portions of 2.43 to 3.29 $\times 10^{-3}$ molar solutions of the sample in 50% aqueous (triple distilled water) acetone. These solutions were stored in the dark. The solvent was equilibrated in a closed vessel in the water bath for 30 min before mixing with the bromides. The solution was continuously stirred with a submersible magnetic stirrer powered with the water of the bath by a (Little Giant) submersible motor. The cell was mounted in one hole stopper and inserted into the solution immediately after addition of the bromide to form a closed system.

Then readings at equal time intervals were taken until there was no increase in conductance between readings. At the beginning of the reaction the conductance was negligible; it increased, however,

markedly during solvolysis owing to the formation of the highly ionized hydrogen bromide.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of rate constants: Solvolysis of benzyl bromide followed first order rate expression given by the equation

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} \quad (1)$$

where k is the specific rate constant, x is the amount of the benzyl bromide used up after time t , and a is the initial concentration of the benzyl bromide. Considering times t_1 and t_2 , it is seen that equation (1) yields

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t_2 - t_1} \log \frac{a - x_1}{a - x_2} \quad (2)$$

Hence, if $(t_2 - t_1)$ is a constant time interval, then

$$\frac{a - x_1}{a - x_2} = C \quad (3)$$

where C is a constant equal to the slope. Rearranging and (3) becomes

$$x_1 = Cx_2 - a(C - 1) \quad (4)$$

It is seen from (4) that a plot of various measured alternate values of conductance (the first reading against the third, the second against the fourth, etc.) of x_1 vs. x_2 , is a straight line with a positive slope C as shown in Fig. 1 and 2. The logarithm of the slope C multiplied by $2.303/\Delta t$, where Δt is a constant time interval, gave the k value of the benzyl bromides given in Table 1. These plots of alternate conductance values (x_1) vs. alternate conductance values (x_2) provide an alternative method for the calculation of the rates of solvolysis of benzyl bromides.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AND ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION FOR SOLVOLYSIS OF BENZYL BROMIDES IN 50% AQUEOUS ACETONE

Compound	T °C	$k \times 10^{-5}$ ssc ⁻¹	T °C	$k \times 10^{-5}$ sec ⁻¹	T °C	$k \times 10^{-5}$ sec ⁻¹	E _a Kcal/mole
Benzyl bromide	45	4.60	50	4.72	55	10.50	19.02
<i>p</i> -Carbomethoxy-benzyl bromide	45	0.78	50	0.94	55	2.53	20.52
2,4-dicyano-benzyl bromide	45	0.27	50	0.55	55	0.79	27.57

Fig. 1 Conductivity Plot for the solvolysis of 2,4-Dicyano-benzyl Bromide at 45°

Fig. 2 Conductivity plots for the solvolysis of *p*-Carbomethoxybenzyl Bromide at 45°

Work is in progress to extend the present work by studying the rates of solvolysis of 2,4-dicarbomethoxybenzyl bromide, 2,6-dicarbomethoxy-, 2,6-dicyano-, and 2,6-dichlorobenzyl bromides and compare it with the mono substituted of *o*- and *p*-Carbomethoxybenzyl bromide.

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